

Blending History with Fictions in *The Glass Place* - Amitav Ghosh

Paper Id : 19278 Submission Date : 2024-09-15 Acceptance Date : 2024-09-23 Publication Date : 2024-09-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.
For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>

Meeta Ghosh

Research Scholar
Department Of English
Sparsh Himalaya
University
Dehradun, Uttarakhand,
India

Nidhi Upadhyay

Supervisor
Department Of English
Sparsh Himalaya
University
Dehradun, Uttarakhand,
India

Abstract Amitav Ghosh's *The Glass Palace* stands as a seminal work that intricately blends historical events with fictional narratives, creating a multi-generational saga that spans across Burma, India, and Malaya. Ghosh's narrative technique of intertwining personal lives with larger historical movements, particularly focusing on the impact of British colonialism, World War II, and the Burmese independence struggle. Through detailed historical descriptions, Ghosh reconstructs pivotal moments, such as the fall of the Burmese monarchy and the rise of the Indian National Army, while infusing his fictional characters with rich, memoir-like reflections that offer personal insights into these grand events. The novel's non-linear timeline allows for the fluid movement between the past and present, showcasing how individual memories shape and are shaped by history. Ghosh seamlessly integrates real historical figures, such as King Thebaw and Queen Supayalat, with fictional characters like Rajkumar and Dolly, creating a layered narrative that explores the complexities of colonialism, migration, and identity. Furthermore, it examines how Ghosh's detailed depiction of everyday life during times of political upheaval humanizes historical events, making them accessible and emotionally resonant for the reader. By merging historical documentation with fictional storytelling, Ghosh challenges the boundaries between fact and fiction, raising questions about the nature of historical truth and the role of memory in shaping our understanding of the past.

Keywords Historical Fiction, British Empire, World War II, Burma, Personal Memory, Collective Memory, Migration, Non-Linear Narrative, Blending History And Fiction.

Introduction In *The Glass Palace*, Amitav Ghosh intricately blends history with fiction, using real historical events as the backdrop for the personal stories of his fictional characters. The novel, set primarily in Burma, India, and Malaya, spans over a century from the British invasion of Burma in 1885 to the 20th century, focusing on colonialism, war, and migration. Ghosh's weaving of history and fiction is seamless, as historical events shape the lives of his characters, yet the personal and emotional experiences give depth to these historical moments. One of the key ways in which Ghosh blends history with fiction is by embedding real historical events within the personal lives of his characters. The novel begins with the British annexation of Burma in 1885, an event that forces King Thebaw and Queen Supayalat into exile in India. This real historical occurrence sets the stage for the fictional narrative.

Objective of study This paper argues that *The Glass Palace* serves not only as a historical novel but also as a reflective meditation on the ways in which personal and collective histories are intertwined. Ultimately, Ghosh's blending of history with fiction offers a nuanced perspective on the colonial legacy and its lasting effects on individuals and nations.

Review of Literature "In Mandalay, you could still feel the breath of the British Empire, but in Rangoon, there was no need for breath – the Empire was the air itself."

This quote reflects the imperial dominance of the British in Burma, giving the reader a sense of the historical context in which the characters live. The tension of British colonialism is ever-present in the characters' lives, but the novel also shows how personal relationships and individual stories unfold against this historical backdrop. Historical element in *The Glass Palace* is the role of the Indian National Army (INA) during World War II. Arjun, a character in the novel, joins the British Indian Army and later shifts allegiances to fight for the INA under Subhas Chandra Bose. Ghosh explores

the internal conflict of loyalty to the British versus the desire for Indian independence, highlighting how global historical events intersect with the personal struggles of the characters.

"Arjun's sense of belonging was shaken; he was a man in uniform, but his uniform had betrayed him."

This reflects Arjun's disillusionment with colonial power structures, while also showing the personal conflicts arising from larger historical movements. Ghosh captures the INA's significance while grounding it in Arjun's personal experiences.

The novel deals extensively with the theme of migration, another historical phenomenon brought about by British colonialism. Rajkumar, one of the main characters, is an Indian orphan who migrates to Burma, where he builds his fortune in the teak industry. His journey reflects the larger historical migrations of Indians to Burma during the British colonial period.

"History is like an ocean, constantly moving and shifting, and we are no more than a pebble in the tide. Our lives are shaped by its currents."

This line reflects Ghosh's view on history individuals are shaped by historical forces beyond their control. Rajkumar's journey is fictional, but it mirrors the real experiences of many who migrated across the British Empire during colonial rule.

Main Text

The Japanese invasion and occupation of Burma during World War II is another historical event that plays a crucial role in the novel. Ghosh captures the chaos and displacement caused by the war, particularly through the experiences of refugees fleeing Burma. This historical event disrupts the lives of the characters and pushes them into exile, much like the Burmese royal family was exiled at the beginning of the novel.

"For the first time, Rajkumar saw that history could happen without warning there was no way of telling when it would strike, or why."

Ghosh reflects on the unpredictability of historical events and their power to change lives in an instant, a theme central to *The Glass Palace*. The Japanese occupation forces the characters to confront the harsh realities of war and displacement, showing how fiction can humanize historical events.

Ghosh also includes real historical figures alongside his fictional creations. Subhas Chandra Bose, for example, appears in the novel during Arjun's involvement with the INA. Ghosh presents these figures in a fictionalized context, allowing readers to explore both the historical reality and the imaginative possibilities of their actions and influence.

"Bose spoke of freedom, and for a moment, Arjun felt the stirring of a deeper loyalty, not to a flag or an army, but to something greater."

By incorporating historical figures like Bose, Ghosh strengthens the connection between his fictional characters and the real history they inhabit, showing how personal and political struggles often overlap.

Through *The Glass Palace*, Amitav Ghosh masterfully intertwines fiction with historical events, creating a narrative that feels both intimate and expansive. The personal stories of the characters are deeply shaped by historical forces, yet their emotional journeys make these historical events accessible and poignant for the reader. The novel explores how history shapes individual lives, and how, in turn, individuals influence and are influenced by the currents of history.

In *The Glass Palace*, Amitav Ghosh uses historical events as the foundation of the novel, weaving them into the lives of the fictional characters. These real events ground the narrative and lend it a sense of authenticity, allowing readers to experience history from the perspectives of individuals who live through these transformative periods.

Amitav Ghosh's *The Glass Palace* intertwines personal narratives with significant historical events, primarily focusing on Burma (Myanmar), India, and Malaya (Malaysia) during the late 19th and 20th centuries. The novel highlights themes of colonialism, war, displacement, and resistance, making history an integral part of the plot.

One of the central historical moments is the British invasion of Burma and the subsequent exile of King Thibaw and Queen Supayalat to India. The novel opens with the fall of Mandalay, the capital of Burma, to British forces. Ghosh vividly describes the forced exile of the royal family and the looting of the Glass Palace .

"In the spring of the year 1885, the British sent a new commander to Burma. King Thibaw and Queen Supayalat were placed under house arrest, and British troops occupied the Glass Palace."

The novel explores the British Empire's exploitation of Burma's natural resources, especially teak, and the forced labor and economic hardship faced by the native population. Rajkumar, the protagonist, builds his wealth through the teak business, which thrives due to British colonization and industrial demand.

“In the Burma of Rajkumar’s childhood, teak was as much a symbol of wealth as the ivory of Africa or the spices of the East. A single tree could fetch more money than a bullock-cart-load of rice.”

The novel covers the Japanese invasion of Burma during World War II (1941–1942), leading to the forced migration of many Indians living in Burma. The mass exodus is a critical moment in the novel. Rajkumar’s family, like many others, is forced to flee Burma during the Japanese invasion, leading to personal and economic loss.

“The great road south from Burma to India was a living river of humanity, people walking, carrying babies and old people, dragging cows and goats, everyone trying to escape the advancing Japanese army.”

The novel reflects the impact of Indian nationalism and the struggle for independence from British rule. The characters grapple with their identities in the context of a changing political landscape. Dinu, Rajkumar’s son, becomes involved in the Indian nationalist movement, reflecting the anti-colonial sentiment of the time.

“There are some people, like my father, who believe that the war for independence will end in disappointment. But we young people, we cannot afford to lose hope.”

The Glass Palace delves deeply into the idea of displacement, not just through war but also through economic migration under colonial rule. Indians are transported to Burma and Malaya as laborers, creating complex diasporic communities. Rajkumar’s journey from being a poor boy in Burma to a wealthy timber merchant symbolizes the displacement of individuals during colonial rule.

“We are like herds of cattle, shipped from one part of the Empire to another, wherever there’s work to be done.”

The novel concludes with Burma’s own nationalist struggle and eventual independence from British rule in 1948, leaving readers with a sense of the post-colonial challenges that the country faces. The political unrest and resistance against British colonialism are mirrored in the lives of the characters who witness the transition to independence.

“The British will go, as they have in India. But the damage has been done, the cracks are deep.”

The Glass Palace, Amitav Ghosh masterfully blends history with fiction to create a sweeping narrative that explores both personal and political transformations over more than a century. The novel focuses on various key themes and topics, intertwining historical events with the lives of its fictional characters. Here are the main topics included in *The Glass Palace*. The British colonization of Burma (Myanmar), India, and Malaya (Malaysia) is central to the novel. Ghosh explores the economic exploitation, cultural displacement, and political subjugation caused by British imperialism. The novel begins with the British invasion of Burma in 1885, which led to the exile of King Thibaw and the colonization of the country.

The impact of World War II, especially the Japanese invasion of Burma, plays a significant role in the novel. War leads to displacement, as thousands of people, including the Indian community living in Burma, are forced to flee. The fall of Rangoon and the mass exodus of Indian migrants from Burma during the Japanese occupation highlight the theme of displacement due to war. Ghosh explores themes of migration and diaspora through the characters who move across geographical boundaries due to colonial rule, economic opportunities, or war. Characters like Rajkumar rise from poverty to wealth through migration, while others experience dislocation and loss. The movement of Indian laborers to Burma and Malaya under British rule, and their later struggles during the war, creates a complex narrative of identity, belonging, and displacement.

The novel touches on the rise of nationalist movements in Burma and India, as the colonies struggle for independence from British rule. Characters such as Dinu become involved in nationalist activities, reflecting the growing resistance to colonial power. The Indian independence movement and Burma’s fight for freedom are important backdrops in the novel, blending real historical struggles with fictional experiences.

Ghosh highlights how colonial powers extracted natural resources like teak from Burma to fuel their industries. Rajkumar’s wealth is built on the timber trade, reflecting the economic exploitation of Burma’s natural resources by British interests. The timber

industry in Burma was a significant part of the British colonial economy, and the novel's detailed portrayal of this industry illustrates the economic consequences of colonialism. The novel portrays the fall of the Burmese monarchy and the exile of King Thibaw and Queen Supayalat to India. The royal family's loss of power symbolizes the broader decline of indigenous rule in the face of European imperialism.

The real-life exile of King Thibaw in 1885 marked the end of the Konbaung Dynasty and the beginning of direct British rule in Burma, an event central to the novel's opening.

While history plays a major role, the novel is also a multi-generational family saga, focusing on the personal lives, relationships, and conflicts of its characters. The different generations experience colonialism, war, and migration in various ways, reflecting changing social and political landscapes. The family dynamics, especially between Rajkumar, his children, and their descendants, reflect how historical forces shape individual destinies. The novel questions the meaning of home, identity, and belonging in a world of displacement and shifting political borders. Characters struggle with their identities as colonial subjects, migrants, and members of diasporic communities.

Ghosh examines how individuals and families redefine themselves in the context of national and cultural upheavals caused by colonialism and war. Ghosh explores how history is remembered, interpreted, and passed down through generations. The characters' personal memories intersect with broader historical events, creating a narrative that reflects on the nature of history itself.

Conclusion

The novel's non-linear structure, with its shifting timelines and multiple perspectives, mirrors the complex ways in which history is experienced and remembered by individuals. Ghosh's ability to weave personal stories into major historical moments makes the novel a powerful exploration of the impact of history on individual lives and societies.

References

1. Ghosh, Amitav. *The Glass Palace*. HarperCollins, 2000.
2. Hawley, John C. "The Glass Palace by Amitav Ghosh." *World Literature Today*, vol. 75, no. 2, 2001, pp. 145-146.
3. Sharma, Kajal. "Narrating History: Amitav Ghosh's *The Glass Palace*." *Journal of Postcolonial Writing*, vol. 42, no. 2, 2006, pp. 149-159.
4. Mukherjee, Meenakshi. "The Anxiety of Indianness: Our Novels in English." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 28, no. 48, 1993, pp. 2607-2611.
5. Brendon, Piers. *The Decline and Fall of the British Empire, 1781-1997*. Knopf, 2008.
6. Daiya, Kavita. "Home and the Nation: Reading Amitav Ghosh's *The Glass Palace*." *MELUS*, vol. 31, no. 3, 2006, pp. 121-142.
7. Tickell, Alex. "Amitav Ghosh's *The Glass Palace* and the Postcolonial Historical Novel." *The Journal of Commonwealth Literature*, vol. 38, no. 1, 2003, pp. 95-110.
8. Mondal, Anshuman A. *Amitav Ghosh*. Manchester University Press, 2007.
9. Sharma, Kajal. "Narrating History: Amitav Ghosh's *The Glass Palace*." *Journal of Postcolonial Writing*, vol. 42, no. 2, 2006, pp. 149-159.
10. Upstone, Sara. *Spatial Politics in the Postcolonial Novel*. Ashgate, 2009.